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FarFish

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Responsive Results-Based Management and capacity building for EU Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement- and international waters

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Authors	Jónas R. Viðarsson	MATIS	26/11/2021	JRV
WP leader	Mary Frances Davidson	GRO-FTP	26/11/2021	MFD
Coordinator	Jónas R. Viðarsson	MATIS	26/11/2021	JRV
Admin. manager	Oddur M. Gunnarsson	MATIS	26/11/2021	OMG

Deliverable D7.13

Report on the concluding symposium

26/11/2021

The FarFish final conference

The FarFish project facilitated an international final conference in the last month of the project. The aim of the conference was to disseminate key results of the project to the external community and stakeholders interested in the subject. The conference had been planned as a physical event in Brussels but was in the end run as an online event, due to COVID.

The conference consisted of 13 presentations and panel discussions, as shown in the agenda below.

FarFish Final Conference November 10th, 2021		
Time (CET)	Title of presentation	Presenter
09:00	Welcome and project introduction	Jonas R. Viðarsson - Matis
09:20	Stakeholder participation in FarFish	Duarte F. Vidal - CETMAR
09:30	Governance analysis in the case studies	Ingrid Kvalvik - Nofima
09:40	Value chain analysis in the case studies	Gregoire Touron-Gardic - UoP
09:50	Management Recommendations	Ragnhildur Friðriksdóttir - Matis
10:00	Tools developed in FarFish	Margarita Rincón - IEO/CSIC
10:10	Break	
10:30	Capacity building within FarFish	Mary Frances - GROFTP
10:40	The EU fleet & FarFish	Alexandre Rodriguez - LDAC
10:50	Fisheries in international waters & FarFish	Juliana Galvao - USP
11:00	The Cabo Verde case study	Benvindo Fonseca - IMAR
11:10	The Senegal case study	Mamadou Diallo - COREWAM
11:20	The Mauritanian case study	Mamadou Dia - IMROP
11:30	The Seychelles case study	Yannick Roucou - SFA
11:40	Break	
12:00	Panel discussions / Impact	Chair: Mary Frances-GROFTP
12:50	Sum-up and closing	Jonas R. Viðarsson - Matis

The agenda of the FarFish final conference

The presentations had been pre-recorded and translated to English, Spanish and French, and the panel discussions were as well translated (live) to the same languages.

A total of 128 participants from 88 companies/organisations and 30 countries attended the conference. The geographical distribution of the attendees can be seen in the following table.

Number of conference attendees by country

Country	No. of attendees
Algeria	1
Argentina	3
Bangladesh	1
Belgium	7
Brazil	7
Cape Verde	3
China	1
Faroe Islands	3
France	3
Germany	1
Ghana	1
Greece	1
Iceland	9
Indonesia	1
Italy	1
Madagascar	1
Mauritania	2
Mauritius	2
Morocco	3
Mozambique	1
Netherlands	1
New Zealand	1
Norway	11
Pakistan	1
Panama	1
Portugal	9
Senegal	9
Seychelles	2
Spain	30
United Kingdom	11
Total	128

The conference ran as planned and without any technical difficulties. The attendees were mostly happy with the conference and considered it as a success. The importance of providing translations was highlighted by the non-EU participants, as well as the fact that having the event online allowed a big group of stakeholders to attend.

All of the conference proceedings (in all three languages) are available on the FarFish webpage <https://www.farfish.eu/farfish-final-conference/> where it will be maintained for at least the next three years.

